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on
RELEVANCE OF MODERN LIBRARIES
IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RELIGION
CULTURE AND RESEARCH**

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Venue

Department of Library and Information Science
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Udaipur-313 001, Rajasthan

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Article for National Seminar

Inbox

Dr. Krishna Kumar Kesharwani <kesharwani67@gmail.com> Thu, Mar 5, 7:04 PM
(3 days ago)

to P, jai, bcc: vivek

Dear Dr. P.S. Rajput

Good Evening

Find the attachment herewith for your reference and necessary action.

Thank you very much

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(DR. K. K. KESHARWANI)

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Dr. P S Rajput

Fri, Mar 6, 1:07 PM
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to me

I am glad to inform you that **your paper has been accepted for presentation and publication in conference volume.**

Registered yourself

Thanks

--

With Regards

Dr. P.S. Rajput

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Sci-Hub Plundering the Academic Publishing Establishment

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Abstract :

The website Sci-Hub enables users to download PDF versions of scholarly articles, including many articles that are paywalled at their journal's site. Sci-Hub has grown rapidly since its creation in 2011, but the extent of its coverage has been unclear. Here we report that, as of March 2017, Sci-Hub's database contains 68.9% of the 81.6 million scholarly articles registered with Crossref and 85.1% of articles published in toll access journals. DANIEL S HIMMELSTEIN find that coverage varies by discipline and publisher, and that Sci-Hub preferentially covers popular, paywalled content. For toll access articles, it is find that Sci-Hub provides greater coverage than the University of Pennsylvania, a major research university in the United States and other universities around the world. Green open access (green open access is where an author publishes their article in any journal and then self-archives a copy in a freely accessible institutional or specialist online archive known as a repository, or on a website.) to toll access articles via technical licit services, on the other hand, remains quite limited. Browse at <https://greenelab.github.io/scihub> it shows Sci-Hub's article coverage, till March 2017, for each scholarly publisher and Sci-Hub's article coverage. For the first time, nearly all scholarly literature is freely available to anyone with an Internet connection, the toll access business model by the publishers may become unsustainable.

Keywords : Repository, Copy-Right, Piracy, Hacking, E-Publishing, Digital Object Identifier

(DOI), Open Access, and Scientific Publishing

Introduction

Access to the research literature is essential to the successful work of re-searchers and the education of the general public. Scientists and the general public rely on a wide range of channels to access the research literature printed issues of journals, interlibrary loans, publishers' online platforms

such as Elsevier ScienceDirect, preprint repositories such as ArXiv, institutional and authors' web pages. Many now propose free access to all scientific papers to everybody.

The website Sci-Hub, now in its sixth year of existence, provides gratis access to scholarly literature, despite the continued presence of pay-walls. Sci-Hub brands itself as “the first pirate website in the world to provide mass and public access to tens of millions of research papers.”The website, started in 2011, is run by Alexandra Elbakyan, a graduate student and native of Kazakhstan who now resides in Russia Elbakyan describes herself as motivated to provide universal access to knowledge. Sci-Hub does not restrict itself to only openly licensed content. Instead, it retrieves and distributes scholarly literature without regard to copy-right. Readers should note that, in many jurisdictions, use of Sci-Hub may constitute copyright infringement. Users of Sci-Hub do so at their own risk. This study is not an endorsement of using Sci-Hub, and its authors and publishers accept no responsibility on behalf of readers. There is a possibility that Sci-Hub users especially those not using privacy-enhancing services such as Tor — could have their usage history unmasked and face legal or reputational consequences.

Sci-Hub is currently served at domains including <https://sci-hub.hk>, <https://sci-hub.la>, <https://sci-hub.mn>, <https://sci-hub.name>, <https://sci-hub.tv>, and <https://sci-hub.tw>, as well as at scihub22266oqxt.onion — a Tor Hidden Service. Elbakyan described the project's technical scope in July 2017: “Sci-Hub technically is by itself a repository, or a library if you like, and not a search engine for some other repository. But of course, the most important part in Sci-Hub is not a repository, but the script that can download papers closed behind paywalls.”One method Sci-Hub uses to bypass paywalls is by obtaining leaked authentication credentials for educational institutions (Elbakyan, 2017). These credentials enable Sci-Hub to use institutional networks as proxies and gain subscription journal access. While the open access movement has progressed slowly (Björk, 2017), Sci-Hub represents a seismic shift in access to scholarly literature. Since its inception, Sci-Hub has experienced sustained growth, with spikes in interest and awareness driven by legal proceedings, service outages, news coverage, and social media.

Figure-Shows Sci-Hub's Growth

The letters A, B, C . . . refer to the following events as in above figure :

- A : Created by Alexandra Elbakyan, the Sci-Hub website goes live on September 5, 2011.
- B : Several LibGen domains go down when their registration expires.
- C : Elsevier files a civil suit against Sci-Hub and LibGen — at the respective domains sci-hub.org and libgen.org — in the U.S.District Court for the Southern District of New York . The complaint seeks a

“prayer for relief” that includes domain name seizure, damages, and “an order disgorging Defendants’ profits”.

D: Elsevier is granted a preliminary injunction to suspend domain names and restrain the site operators from distributing Elsevier’s copyrighted works . Shortly after, Sci-Hub and LibGen resurface at alternative domains outside of U.S. court jurisdiction, including on the dark web.

E: The article “Meet the Robin Hood of Science” by Simon Oxenham spurs a wave of attention and news coverage on Sci-Hub and Alexandra Elbakyan (Oxenham, 2016), culminating in The New York Times asking “Should all research papers be free?”

F: The article “Who’s downloading pirated papers? Everyone” by John Bohannon shows Sci-Hub is used worldwide, including in developed countries (Bohannon, 2016b). These findings spark debate among scholars, with a large contingent of scientists supporting Sci-Hub’s mission (Woolston, 2016; Travis, 2016).

G: Alexandra Elbakyan is named one of “Nature’s 10”, which featured “ten people who mattered” in 2016 (Van Noorden, 2016). This article profiles Alexandra and includes an estimate that Sci-Hub serves “3% of all downloads from science publishers worldwide.”

H: The court finds that Alexandra Elbakyan, Sci-Hub, and LibGen are “liable for willful copyright infringement” in a default judgment, since none of the defendants answered Elsevier’s complaint (Schiermeier, 2017a; Van der Sar, 2017a; Sweet, 2017). The court issues a permanent injunction and orders the defendants to pay Elsevier \$15 million, or \$150,000 for each of 100 copyrighted works. The statutory damages, which the defendants do not intend to pay, now bear interest.

I: The American Chemical Society files suit against Sci-Hub in the U.S. District Court for the Eastern District of Virginia. Their “prayer for relief” requests that Internet search engines and Internet service providers “cease facilitating access” to Sci-Hub (Van der Sar, 2017b; Barnes A et al., 2017).

J: The version 1 preprint of this study is published (Himmelstein et al., 2017a), generating headlines such as Science’s “subscription journals are doomed” (McKenzie, 2017) and Inside Higher Ed’s “Inevitably Open” (Fister, 2017).

K: Sci-Hub blocks access to Russian IP addresses due to disputes with the Russian Scientific establishment and the naming of a newly discovered parasitoid wasp species, *Idiogramma elbakyanae*, after Alexandra Elbakyan (Standish, 2017; Khalaim and Ruiz-Cancino, 2017). Four days later, Sci-Hub restores access after receiving “many letters of support from Russian researchers”.

L: The court rules on the American Chemical Society suit, ordering Sci-Hub to pay \$4.8 million in damages and that “any person or entity in active concert or participation” with Sci-Hub “including any Internet search engines, web hosting and Internet service providers, domain name registrars, and domain name registries, cease facilitating access” (Schiermeier, 2017b; Brinkema L, 2017). Within five weeks, the domains sci-hub.io, sci-hub.ac, sci-hub.cc, and sci-hub.bz were suspended by their respective domain name registries (Silver, 2017), leaving only the Tor hidden service and severally registered/ revealed domains in operation.

Does SCI-HUB'S Pirated Papers Mean the end of Subscription Journals ?

Elsevier is a giant in the academic publishing industry. In 2010, the company made just over £74M in profits. So why is a giant like Elsevier battling it out in court with guerilla websites like Sci-Hub and LibGen? For starters, it’s important to understand what makes scientific publishing so profitable. Publishers like Elsevier accept submissions of work already done by scientists. These undergo a strict peer-review process conducted by scientists, who work voluntarily. Only a fraction of these submissions is published and Elsevier sells the published materials to universities, libraries, and other institutions.

The business model of scientific publishers is so lucrative that a 2005 Deutsche Bank report called it a “triple-pay” system. The profits only multiply as closed access journals like JSTOR curate their collections even further, creating an edge against the competition. In certain cases, the competition comes from open access websites like Sci-Hub, which are built on copyright infringement and academic piracy.

SCI-HUB'S Coverage -Coverage by Journal Attributes :

Article coverage according to journal attributes. Sci-Hub covered 83.1% of the 56,755,671 articles that were attributable to a journal. Articles from inactive journals had slightly lower coverage than active journals (77.3% versus 84.1%). Strikingly, coverage was substantially higher for articles from toll rather than open access journals (85.1% versus 48.3%). Coverage did vary by subject area, with the highest coverage in chemistry at 93.0% and the lowest coverage in computer science at 76.3%. Accordingly, no discipline had coverage below 75%.

Each bar represents Sci-Hub’s coverage of articles in journals with the specified attributes, according to Scopus. Active refers to whether a journal still publishes articles. Open refers to whether a journal is open access. Subject area refers to a journal’s discipline. Note that some journals are assigned to multiple subject areas.

Coverage by publisher :

Coverage by Category of Access Status :

This category of access is frequently referred to as “gold” open access, meaning that all articles from the journal are available gratis. However, articles in toll access journals may also be available without charge. Adopting the terminology from the recent “State of OA” study (Piwowar et al., 2018), articles in toll access journals may be available gratis from the publisher under a license that permits use (termed “hybrid”) or with all rights reserved (termed “bronze”). Alternatively, “green” articles are paywalled on the publisher’s site, but available gratis from an open access repository (e.g. a pre- or post-print server, excluding Sci-Hub and academic social networks). The State of OA study determined the access status of 290,120 articles using the Open Access Digital Objective Identifier (OADOI) utility.

SCI-HUB'S Business Model :

Pirate websites like Sci-Hub are undermining the business model of academic publishers with its own model. Sci-Hub's business model is hard to pinpoint. Presently, all that is known is that Alexandra Elbakyan, a Kazakhstani, built Sci-Hub because she believes in radical open access. The site operates from Russia, but nothing is known as about its host, its servers, and its domains. A recent manuscript written by Himmelstein et al. reveals the extent of Sci-Hub's problematic engagement with the academic publishing industry. Himmelstein and colleagues found that Sci-Hub's database contains 85.2% of all articles published in closed access journals. Unsurprisingly, Sci-Hub's coverage of Elsevier is at 97.3%. Sci-Hub is a threat to the scientific publishing community because it is essentially a hacker and a pirate. A closer look at the extent of Sci-Hub's coverage will reveal the extent of its piracy.

The Problem with SCI-HUB :

Himmelstein and colleagues revealed that Sci-Hub offers 56,246,220 articles. This equates to 68.9% of all journal articles from active and inactive journals. Coverage by article type was surprising: Sci-Hub covered 77.8% of journal articles, 79.7% of proceedings, and 14.2% of books. Peer-reviewed scientific articles are available on the site for researchers, or anyone, to download and use. Coverage by year varies, with most years since 1850 having an annual coverage between 60-80%. However, Sci-Hub's coverage for the year 2010 and beyond dwindled, in part because users had to submit a request for articles to be downloaded onto Sci-Hub's servers. Another striking finding is that coverage was significantly higher for closed rather than open access journals (85.2% vs. 49.1%). Accordingly, highly cited journals were more likely to be covered by Sci-Hub. In order to access an article, a user has to make a request on Sci-Hub. Himmelstein and colleagues found that 99.3% of all these requests were fulfilled. Nearly 100% of all requests for journal articles were fulfilled. Sci-Hub also accepts donations through Paypal, QiQi, WebMoney, Yandex, and bitcoins. Himmelstein et al. estimated the current price of bitcoins donated to Sci-Hub at \$175,000. It's clear, however, that Sci-Hub is not a business. Elbakyan said that as a student, she found the fees for accessing closed publications as "just insane." She vies for open access. Sci-Hub was born after she teamed up with other academics on the internet. However, publishers like Elsevier and journals such as the American Chemical Society (ACS) have filed lawsuits against Elbakyan because of piracy, hacking, and copyright infringement.

Conclusion :

Even if Sci-Hub fancies itself as "white-hat" hackers, it is still a hindrance to the real meaning of science and knowledge. For one, copyrights exist for a reason, and that is to deter intellectual property theft. Sci-Hub is stealing from closed access publishers, in effect, because it bypasses paywalls. Secondly, the academic publishing community does not look kindly on research pirates, and for good reason.

Scientific publications invest a lot of time, money, and effort into curating the articles that they publish. The sole aim of this is to ensure only research articles that are accurate, timely, and methodologically-sound are published. Third, curating scientific articles keeps the scientific community up-to-to-date, relevant, and informed of verified knowledge.

The issue with Sci-Hub is especially relevant today because it lies at the cusp between open access and closed access content. For the past couple of years, the academic publishing community has been engaged in a debate with researchers about open access. Sci-Hub highlights this debate. It is unlikely that the debate will be resolved soon unless a new internet protocol is formulated that can somehow satisfy the needs of both publishers and academics. For now, academic publishers need to be cautious and vigilant. After all, they could be educating the next generation of Sci-Hub creators.

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